

Table 1. Crop establishment, growth parameters, grain yield, and yield components of direct seeded rice in the Mekong Delta.^a CLRRRI, 1993 wet season.

Cultivar	Seedlings ^b / m ² (no.)	TDM ^b at flowering (g/m ²)	TDM ^b at maturity (g/m ²)	LAI ^b at flowering	Harvest index ^b (%)	Spikelets/ m ² (no. × 10 ³)	Panicles ^c / m ² (no.)	Spikelets ^c / panicle (no.)	Filled spikelets ^c (%)	1,000 grain weight ^c (g)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
IR41996-50-2-1-3	400 a	455 c	740 b	2.20 b	47.0 a	23.4 c	527 a	44 d	76.6 a	29.5 a	2.87 d
IR52341-60-1-2-1	406 a	561 c	953 ab	1.53 c	47.0 a	28.9 bc	446 a	65 c	73.9 a	27.5 b	3.77 bcd
IR31802-48-2-2-2	401 a	455 c	811 b	1.93 bc	41.0 b	37.1 b	527 a	70 c	63.4 b	24.0 c	3.40 cd
MTL 114 (check)	375 b	734 b	1134 a	3.47 a	44.0 ab	39.1 b	479 a	82 c	73.8 a	27.7 b	4.80 abc
MTL 103 (check)	379 b	713 b	1020 ab	3.50 a	47.0 a	36.5 b	471 a	77 c	80.2 a	28.1 b	5.13 ab
BR736-20-3-1	407 a	870 a	1110 a	3.87 a	42.0 ab	55.4 a	410 a	135 a	78.7 a	21.5 e	5.20 ab
BR1870-67-1-3	400 a	840 a	1114 a	4.00 a	45.0 ab	55.8 a	442 a	126 b	80.3 a	22.7 d	5.83 a

^aMeans in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^bSampled from 0.5 m² per plot. ^cAnalyzed from 20 panicles per plot. ^dHarvested from 5 m² per plot.

Table 2. Coefficients of simple linear correlations between the characters associated with grain yield.^a

Character	Two	Three	Four	Five	Six	Seven	Eight	Nine	Ten	Eleven
One	-0.17	-0.33	0.36	-0.21	0.19	0.12	-0.14	-0.48	-0.20	-0.28
Two		0.94**	0.91**	-0.84*	0.90**	0.86*	0.67*	-0.55	-0.15	0.95**
Three			0.79*	-0.80*	0.78*	0.75	0.51	-0.42	-0.14	0.92**
Four				-0.55	0.79*	0.80*	0.66	-0.45	-0.16	0.90**
Five					-0.79*	-0.69	-0.60	0.53	0.02	-0.75
Six						0.98**	0.42	-0.86*	-0.45	0.84*
Seven							0.33	-0.88**	-0.53	0.84*
Eight								0.02	0.55	0.62
Nine									0.73	-0.52
Ten										-0.10

^a* = significant at the 5% level; ** = significant at the 1% level. 1 = seedlings (no./m²), 2 = TDM accumulation at flowering, 3 = TDM accumulation at maturity, 4 = LAI at flowering, 5 = panicles (no./m²), 6 = spikelets (no./panicle), 7 = spikelets (no./m²), 8 = filled spikelets (%), 9 = 1,000-grain weight, 10 = harvest index, 11 = yield.

Seven cultivars were used, five of which are tolerant of soil anaerobiosis during seedling establishment. The other two are local checks (Table 1). Pregerminated seeds (2 d old) were sown at 400 seeds/m² (about 100 kg/ha) immediately after puddling the soil (pH 5.2, 0.04% total P, 3.2% organic C, and 0.26% total N). Seeds were beneath the soil surface. A herbicide, Sofit, was sprayed 3 d after sowing (DAS). Fertilizer was applied at 60-17-25 kg NPK/ha at 10 DAS, 30 kg N/ha at 30 DAS, and 60 kg N/ha at 60 DAS. The experiment was laid out in a

randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 20 m².

Number of seedlings established was higher for anaerobic cultivars than for checks. Yields of BR1870-67-1-3 and BR736-20-3-1 were the same as those of the checks, and higher than those of IR52341-60-1-2-1, IR31802-48-2-2-2, and IR41996-50-2-1-3. Difference in yield was due to the difference in total dry matter (TDM) accumulation at maturity and not in harvest index (HI) (Table 1). BR1870-67-1-3 and BR736-20-3-1 had large panicle size, indicated

by the high spikelet number/panicle. Although BR1870-67-1-3 and BR736-20-3-1 had more spikelets/m², they did not outyield checks significantly because their 1,000-grain weights were small.

Correlation analysis showed that the grain yield highly correlated with TDM accumulation at flowering and harvest, spikelets/panicle, spikelets/m², and leaf area index (LAI) at flowering (Table 2).

The significant correlation between spikelets/m² and spikelets/panicle ($r = 0.98^{**}$) indicated that big panicles are important for obtaining a large number of spikelets per unit land area.

The yield recorded for BR1870-67-1-3 was higher than the mean (4.3 t/ha) for the past 7 yr at CLRRRI during the wet season under transplanting (80-25-18 kg NPK/ha). The physiological and morphological traits required for high-yielding direct seeded rice in the Mekong Delta in the wet season seem to be high TDM accumulation at flowering and harvest, LAI at flowering of about 4, and large panicle size. These characters may be considered when breeding rice for direct seeding in the Mekong Delta. ■

Simulating rice leaffolder feeding effects on yield using MACROS

L. T. Fabellar, N. G. Fabellar, and K. L. Heong, IRRRI

The rice leaffolder (LF), *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, can affect yield by reducing

leaf area. Most previous attempts to relate yield to leaf area removed were probably too simplistic. Systems analysis and simulation approaches may improve our understanding of this relationship.

We conducted an experiment to quantify the reduction in leaf area due to LF feeding. We incorporated the actual

leaf consumption into the MACROS rice model and predicted yield loss at different larval densities and crop ages.

Destructive weekly samplings were taken from five hills of IR36. A LICOR LI-3000 leaf area meter was used to measure total leaf area and leaf area damaged in 1- × 1-m plots infested with 3

second-instar larvae per hill on plants at 40, 60, and 80 d after seeding (DAS). Infested plots were enclosed with open fiberglass cages to prevent larvae from dispersing.

The leaf area damaged by LF larvae was higher on plants at 40 DAS than on plants at 60 and 80 DAS (see table). Leaf consumption, based on actual leaf area damage, was incorporated into the model. Simulation runs were made for each larval density and crop age. (See figure for the simulated leaf area and simulated yield at different larval densities and crop ages.) The model predicted 9, 12, and 30% leaf area reduction on plants at 80, 60, and 40 DAS, respectively, when infested with 20 larvae. Crop response to insect damage seemed to decrease with crop age. The predicted yield reduction was only 3.4% on plants at 40 DAS infested with 20 larvae. The simulated yield reduction was $\leq 1\%$ on plants at 80 and 60 DAS infested with up to 33 larvae. In most ricefields, LF larval populations are rarely more than two per hill.

The results suggest that leaf consumption of 20 larvae seems insufficient to significantly reduce crop yield. This may

Simulated leaf area (a) and simulated yield (b) at different larval densities and crop ages.

Weekly mean leaf area damage on plants infested ($\pm$ SE) by LF at different crop ages.

Sampling time (wk)	Damaged leaf area (cm ²)/hill		
	40 DAS ^a	60 DAS	80 DAS
1	4.52 $\pm$ 0.16	2.58 $\pm$ 0.09	1.99 $\pm$ 0.06
2	10.69 $\pm$ 0.28	6.08 $\pm$ 0.29	4.64 $\pm$ 0.12
3	9.12 $\pm$ 0.33	6.53 $\pm$ 0.22	4.41 $\pm$ 0.04

^aDAS = days after seeding.

be attributed to the rice plant's ability to compensate for damage at early stages. In addition, photosynthesis rates in different leaf layers may increase as a result of damage. Although MACROS

does not have these compensatory components, yield losses predicted were extremely low. Thus, it appears that LF can rarely cause significant yield losses in farmers' fields. ■

Pest resistance

Resistance of Guangxi wild rice to diseases and insect pests

Li Rongbai, Guangxi Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanning, Guangxi 530007, China

Oryza rufipogon and *O. officinalis* are the two kinds of wild rice in Guangxi Province, China. The Institute of Crop Germplasm Resources under the Guangxi Academy of Agricultural Sciences and the Institute of Plant Protection under the Guangxi Agricultural College have cooperated since 1981 to evaluate these wild rices for resistance to blast (BI), bacterial blight (BB), brown planthopper (BPH),

whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), and gall midge (GM) (Table 1).

Of the available accessions, the following are resistant to a particular pest: 23 *O. rufipogon* and 15 *O. officinalis* to BI; 16 *O. rufipogon* and 11 *O. officinalis* to Chinese BB races I-V; 20 *O. rufipogon* to BPH biotypes 1 and 2 (86 *O. officinalis* are highly resistant to BPH); 117 *O. officinalis* to WPBH, with 47 possessing very high resistance; and 8 *O. rufipogon* and 1 *O. officinalis* to GM. These accessions have been recommended as donors of resistance in the national rice breeding program (Table 2). They are conserved in the Nanning Wild Rice Nursery. ■

Table 1. Wild rice resistance to diseases and insect pests.

Species	Disease/insect pest	Accessions evaluated (no.)	Resistant accessions	
			no.	%
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Blast	1587	67	4.1
	Bacterial blight	1553	289	18.6
	Brown planthopper	1214	30	2.5
	Whitebacked planthopper	1236	27	2.2
	Gall midge	1203	8	1.4
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Blast	199	22	11.0
	Bacterial blight	199	194	97.5
	Brown planthopper	198	195	98.5
	Whitebacked planthopper	197	197	100.0
	Gall midge	184	1	0.5